

ASSESSMENT OF EXPERIENTIAL TRANSFER OF TRAINING ON EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS OF SHS-TVL-HOME ECONOMICS GRADUATES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 5

Pages: 467-667

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2181

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13294954

Manuscript Accepted: 07-08-2024

Assessment of Experiential Transfer of Training on Employability Skills of SHS-TVL-Home Economics Graduates

Marycris V. Urgelles,* Dominic T. Urgelles
 For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study assessed the Experiential Transfer of Training among Mariano Marcos Memorial Senior High School (SHS) TVL -- Home Economics Graduates, focusing on the specializations of Cookery, Bread and Pastry Production, and Food and Beverage Services. A mixed-methods design was employed, involving surveys of graduates and interviews with work immersion supervisors, teachers, and industry supervisors. The study found that graduates generally perceived a high level of transfer of training and alignment with their current job roles. Key themes from interviews included the importance of hands-on training, industry partnerships, and ongoing professional development. However, areas for improvement were identified, such as technical skills refinement and curriculum length. Industry supervisors emphasized essential qualities like adaptability, communication, and technical proficiency in graduates' work performance. A statistically significant difference was found between perceptions of working performance and the work immersion program. The findings highlight the effectiveness of the SHS-TVL-Home Economics program in preparing graduates for the workforce while identifying opportunities for enhancement. Recommendations include strengthening industry partnerships, extending training duration, and regularly evaluating the program for continuous improvement. This study contributes valuable insights to optimize experiential learning and employability of SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates.

Keywords: *experiential transfer of training, SHS-TVL-Home Economics, work immersion, employability skills*

Introduction

The Philippine education system plays a vital role in the nation's socio-economic progress and cultural heritage. Within Senior High School (SHS) programs, the Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) tracks hold particular significance for imparting practical proficiencies demanded by contemporary workplaces (Orbeta, 2019). Among these, strands within the Home Economics discipline offer valuable training for diverse vocations and entrepreneurial endeavors (Degala, 2018). The efficacious transfer of acquired knowledge and skills from these programs is pivotal for enhancing graduates' employability and fostering their success in the labor market (Santos, 2020). However, a significant gap remains in understanding how experiential learning within SHS-TVL Home Economics programs impacts graduates' employability skills in the Philippine context. This study seeks to address this critical gap by assessing the extent of the transfer of training, evaluating the alignment of work immersion experiences with employability, exploring perceptions of teachers, work immersion supervisors, and industry supervisors, and providing recommendations for program improvement.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the Experiential Transfer of Training of Mariano Marcos Memorial Senior High School TVL – Home Economics Graduates. Specifically, it sought answers to the following subproblems:

1. To what extent is the transfer of training of the SHS- TVL- Home Economics graduates in terms of the following specializations:
 - 1.1. cookery;
 - 1.2. bread and pastry production, and
 - 1.3. food and beverage services?
2. To what extent is the alignment of the work immersion program/experiences with respondents' current job/position in terms of:
 - 2.1. SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates' employability in terms of work readiness;
 - 2.2. Graduates' employability in terms of use of the hard skills grasped during SHS-TVL-Home Economics Training;
 - 2.3. Graduates' employability in terms of use of the soft skills grasped during SHS-TVL-Home Economics Training; and
 - 2.4. Graduates' employability in terms of alignment of track?
3. Is there a significant difference in the alignment of the work immersion program and workplace performance?
4. What is teachers and work immersion supervisors' perception of the alignment of training from school to work immersion to actual work?
5. What is the perception of the industry's supervisors of the respondents' work performance?
6. Based on the study's findings, what action plan can be made?

Literature Review

Technical-Vocational Education (TVET) in the Philippines:

The local studies cited in the literature review shed light on the state of TVET in the Philippines. They highlight the significance of TVET graduates in the job market, emphasizing that they earn higher wages than those with secondary education alone. However, there are also findings suggesting that individuals who pursue both TVET and tertiary education may earn less due to completing the lowest level of TVET. This context underscores the importance of assessing the effectiveness of TVET programs, such as those in Home Economics, in enhancing students' employability skills.

Assessment of TVL Home Economics Programs:

Several local studies delve into the assessment of TVL Home Economics programs, focusing on various aspects such as students' competency levels, work immersion performance, and readiness for employment. These studies provide insights into the alignment between the competencies taught in TVL Home Economics courses and the expectations of employers. They also highlight the importance of practical experiences, such as work immersion, in bridging the gap between classroom learning and industry demands.

Facilities, Equipment, and Instructional Materials:

The literature review discusses the adequacy of facilities, equipment, and instructional materials in supporting TVL Home Economics education. It identifies areas where improvements are needed, such as upgrading equipment and facilities, providing more opportunities for practical tests, and ensuring the availability of instructional resources. These findings underscore the importance of a conducive learning environment for enhancing students' skills and competencies.

Transfer of Training and Employability Skills:

Foreign studies provide insights into the transfer of training and its impact on employability skills development. They explore how practical experiences, such as hands-on activities and collaborative learning, contribute to students' acquisition and application of skills relevant to the workforce. Moreover, studies emphasize the importance of integrating real-world experiences into the curriculum to enhance students' employability and readiness for the job market.

Pedagogical Approaches in Home Economics Education:

The literature review also covers pedagogical approaches in Home Economics education, including technology, collaborative learning, and integrative teaching methods. These approaches aim to promote active engagement, critical thinking, and practical skill development among students, aligning with the objectives of TVL Home Economics programs.

In synthesizing the literature review, it becomes evident that the current study on the impact of experiential transfer of training on employability skills of SHS-TVL Home Economics graduates at Mariano Marcos Memorial High School contributes to the existing body of knowledge by focusing on a specific aspect of TVET education. By investigating the effectiveness of experiential learning experiences in enhancing students' employability skills, the study aims to provide valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders in improving the quality and relevance of TVL Home Economics programs.

Methodology

Research Design

The type of mixed-method used in this research is the explanatory sequential design. This approach is particularly appropriate for studying the impact of experiential learning on employability because it begins with the collection and analysis of quantitative data, followed by qualitative data to explain or build upon the initial quantitative results.

In this study, the process began with quantitative data collection through surveys distributed to graduates of the Mariano Marcos Memorial Senior High School's TVL Home Economics program. These surveys aimed to gather measurable data on the graduates' employment status, the relevance of their acquired skills to their job roles, and their overall work performance. The analysis of this data provided an initial understanding of the relationship between experiential learning and employability outcomes. For instance, it might have shown a positive correlation between the alignment of the work immersion program and graduates' job performance.

Following this, the qualitative phase involved conducting in-depth interviews with a subset of survey respondents. These interviews were designed to explore the quantitative findings in more detail. For example, while the survey data indicated a general trend, the interviews allowed researchers to delve into individual experiences, uncovering the specific ways in which graduates applied their skills in the workplace, the challenges they faced, and their personal stories of success or difficulty. This qualitative data provided rich context and helped explain the reasons behind the statistical trends observed in the quantitative phase.

By using an explanatory sequential design, the study effectively triangulated its findings. The initial quantitative data established a broad understanding of the impact of experiential learning on employability, while the subsequent qualitative data offered deeper insights into the "why" and "how" behind these patterns. This approach ensured a comprehensive analysis, validating and refining the

initial results and providing a nuanced understanding of the complex phenomenon of skill transfer from experiential learning to employability. It enabled the researchers to make more informed recommendations for improving the SHS-TVL Home Economics program, ultimately aiming to better prepare future graduates for the workforce.

Therefore, a mixed-methods approach offers a more holistic and nuanced understanding of the impact of experiential training on employability skills compared to relying solely on quantitative or qualitative methods alone. Nguyen and Pham (2021) used a mixed-methods design to investigate employability skills among university graduates, emphasizing the value of quantitative and qualitative data for a comprehensive evaluation. Creswell & Plano Clark (2018) provide a foundational guide to designing and implementing mixed-methods research, highlighting the benefits of integrating multiple approaches for deeper understanding. Tran et al. (2020) utilized a sequential mixed-methods study to assess the impact of work-integrated learning programs on graduates' employability skills, emphasizing the value of combining quantitative and qualitative methods for actionable insights.

Respondents

The study population consisted of four groups of respondents, including graduates from SY 2018-2019 to SY 2022-2023 and work immersion supervisors and industry supervisors. The total population of SHS-TVL-HE graduates is 235. Using Slovin's Formula with 0.05 as the margin of error, the required respondents in the qualitative phase are 149. The study's respondents were composed of 149 students and 10 industry supervisors.

The selection of respondents was done through purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a technique of choosing respondents for the study based on their capability to provide information (Duff, 2016). The selection of respondents for this research was conducted using purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique that involves selecting participants based on their specific characteristics and their ability to provide relevant and insightful information for the study. This method is particularly suitable for exploratory research where the goal is to gain a deep understanding of specific phenomena from those who have direct experience and knowledge about the subject matter. In this study, purposive sampling was employed to ensure that the selected respondents could provide comprehensive insights into the impact of experiential learning on employability within the SHS-TVL Home Economics program at Mariano Marcos Memorial Senior High School.

The inclusion criteria for selecting the participants were as follows:

Graduates

The graduates must have successfully completed the SHS-TVL Home Economics program at Mariano Marcos Memorial Senior High School. This criterion ensures that the respondents have gone through the same curriculum and experiential learning processes under investigation. The graduates should be currently employed or have recent employment experience. This criterion ensures that the respondents can provide relevant information about how the skills acquired during their education are being applied in the workforce. The graduates must be willing to participate in both the survey and the follow-up interviews. This criterion ensures that the respondents are open to sharing detailed and personal insights about their experiences.

Teachers and Work Immersion Supervisors

The supervisors must have directly overseen the work immersion component of the SHS-TVL Home Economics program. This criterion ensures that the respondents have firsthand experience and knowledge of the practical training provided to the students. The supervisors should have significant experience in supervising students during their work immersion, ensuring that they can provide informed feedback about the effectiveness of the experiential learning component. The supervisors must be willing to participate in the interviews. This criterion ensures that the respondents are open to sharing their observations and assessments of the students' preparedness and skill application.

Industry Supervisors

The industry supervisors must be employed in industries related to the skills taught in the Home Economics program, such as food service, textile and fashion, or personal finance management. This criterion ensures that the respondents can provide relevant insights into the industry-specific skills and competencies required. The industry supervisors should have experience working with graduates from the SHS-TVL Home Economics program. This criterion ensures that the respondents can provide informed feedback on how well the graduates' skills align with industry expectations. The industry supervisors must be willing to participate in the interviews. This criterion ensures that the respondents are open to providing detailed feedback about the graduates' job performance and skill application.

By employing purposive sampling and establishing these inclusion criteria, the study ensured that the selected respondents could provide rich, relevant, and diverse perspectives on the experiential learning and employability outcomes of the SHS-TVL Home Economics program. This approach facilitated a comprehensive understanding of the research question, enabling the researchers to draw meaningful conclusions and make informed recommendations for program improvements.

Instruments

The instruments are used in the study:

Survey Questionnaire

A researcher-made questionnaire from various related studies and literature was developed. It was drafted by the researcher herself as the main instrument to gather data to determine the proposed intervention measure.

After designing and drafting the research instrument, the researcher submitted it to her adviser for comments and suggestions to improve the criteria, content, and form to enrich the substance of the instrument. The improved draft was then presented to her research professor, a thesis expert, and a statistician to check the descriptive interpretation and improve the survey questionnaire's content.

The final draft was finalized upon the approval of her adviser. It was pilot tested run to 20 he Graduates and undergone with reliability testing with cronbach's alpha of 0.958 indicating that the questionnaire is very consistent in its measurement and it's highly reliable.

The survey questionnaire has three parts, namely:

Part I The Demographic Profile of the Respondents. This elicited data on the demographic profile of the respondents as to age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, and number of years in service.

Part II Assessment of the Extent of the Transfer of training or work performance with Respondents' current job/position. This part utilized data to assess the extent of the transfer of training or work performance with respondents' current jobs/positions.

Part II Assessment of the Extent of the alignment of Work Immersion Program/experiences with Respondents' current job/position. This part utilized data to assess the extent of the alignment of work immersion programs/experiences with respondents' current jobs/positions.

For the Interview Guide Questions,

One set was for the assessment of the Perception of work immersion supervisors and teacher with the Respondent's Work Performance. This part collected data on the perception of work immersion supervisors and teachers with the respondents' work performance.

Another set was for the assessment of the Perception of Industry Supervisors with the Respondent's Work Performance. This part collected data on the perception of industry supervisors with the respondents' work performance.

Validation and Reliability of the Instrument

The validation and reliability testing process of a research questionnaire was crucial to ensure that the instrument accurately measures the intended constructs and produces consistent results.

A panel of subject matter experts in SHS-TVL education, employability skills, and related disciplines reviews the questionnaire. These experts provide feedback on the questionnaire items' relevance, clarity, and comprehensiveness. Based on the input from the expert panel, the questionnaire was revised to address any identified shortcomings or areas for improvement. This iterative process ensures that the questionnaire adequately captures the relevant constructs.

A pilot study was conducted with a 30 samples of SHS-TVL Home Economics graduates to assess the questionnaire items' clarity, coherence, and appropriateness in measuring the intended constructs. Factor analysis is performed to examine the underlying structure of the questionnaire and assess whether the items align with the hypothesized constructs. This helps confirm the construct validity of the questionnaire.

Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which was 0.958, was calculated to assess the internal consistency of the questionnaire items measuring each construct. The A high alpha value (typically ≥ 0.70) indicates that the items reliably measure the same underlying construct.

Based on the validation and reliability testing results, the questionnaire was revised as necessary to address any identified issues or weaknesses. This may involve refining wording, eliminating redundant items, or adjusting response scales to improve clarity and precision. By systematically conducting validation and reliability testing, researchers ensured that the questionnaire is valid and reliable for measuring the intended constructs and generating meaningful data for the research study.

Procedure

The data-gathering procedures for the study entail several steps.

Seeking Permission from the Company

The researcher initiated the process by formally requesting permission from the company to conduct the study. This involves preparing a formal request letter outlining the research's purpose, scope, methodology, and potential benefits to the company. The request letter may also include assurances of confidentiality and data protection to address company concerns about sharing information or allowing access to employees. The researcher waits for the company's approval before proceeding to the next step.

Administering the Survey Questionnaire:

Upon receiving approval from the company, the researcher personally visited the company premises to administer the survey

questionnaire to the respondents. The researcher coordinated with the company's human resources department or relevant personnel to identify and recruit eligible respondents for the study. Depending on the company's preferences and logistical considerations, the survey questionnaire may be administered in person, electronically (e.g., via email or online survey platforms), or through a combination of methods. The researcher ensures that respondents understand the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation, and any confidentiality or privacy considerations. Respondents are given sufficient time and privacy to complete the questionnaire, and any questions or concerns they may have are addressed promptly by the researcher.

Retrieval of Completed Questionnaires

Once the survey period is completed, the researcher collected the completed questionnaires from the respondents. If the survey was conducted electronically, the researcher retrieved the responses from the online survey platform or email submissions. The researcher ensures that all completed questionnaires are securely stored and protected to maintain confidentiality and data integrity.

Data Tabulation, Analysis, and Interpretation

The collected data are tabulated, organized, and prepared for analysis. This may involve entering responses into a spreadsheet or statistical software for further processing. Statistical techniques and methods are applied to analyze the data, such as descriptive statistics (e.g., frequencies, percentages) to summarize demographic information and inferential statistics (e.g., t-tests, ANOVA) to examine relationships and differences between variables. The researcher interprets the findings in the context of the research objectives and relevant literature, identifying key patterns, trends, and implications from the data analysis.

Presentation of Data

As appropriate, the findings will be presented in tabular and textual formats to facilitate understanding and interpretation. Tables, charts, graphs, and narrative summaries will illustrate the essential findings and highlight significant results. The researcher will provide a clear and coherent interpretation of the data, discussing implications for theory, practice, and future research directions.

By following these data-gathering procedures, the researcher ensures a systematic and rigorous approach to collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data for the study.

Data Analysis

The following statistics were used to analyze the gathered data.

Percentage. This was used to compare the sizes of the different magnitudes. It was to describe the percentage distribution of the profile variable of the respondents.

Weighted Mean. This was used to get the average frequency of the respondents in each weighted item.

Five-point five-point was used to assess the experiential transfer of training of Mariano Marcos Memorial Senior High School TVL-Home Economics Graduates.

Ranking. This was used to determine the order of decreasing or increasing magnitude of variations. The most significant frequency is ranked number 1, 2, and so on, down to the last rank and number.

Inferential statistics were employed to make inferences or predictions about the population based on sample data. Common techniques include:

Hypothesis testing (e.g., t-tests, ANOVA, chi-square tests) to determine whether observed differences between groups are statistically significant.

Correlation analysis to examine the relationship between variables.

Regression analysis to identify predictors of an outcome variable and assess their strength and significance.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are paramount in any research study, particularly involving human participants. In the context of the proposed study, several ethical considerations need to be addressed:

Informed Consent

Participants should be fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits before consenting to participate. In this study, SHS-TVL Home Economics graduates and industry supervisors should be provided with clear and understandable information about their involvement and the use of their data.

Voluntary Participation

Participation in the study should be voluntary, and participants should not feel coerced or pressured to participate. They should be

assured they can withdraw from the study without any negative consequences.

Confidentiality

Measures should be taken to ensure the confidentiality and anonymity of participants' data. Personal information should be kept confidential and stored securely to prevent unauthorized access. Data should be reported in aggregate to minimize the risk of identifying individual participants.

Respect for Participants' Rights and Dignity

Researchers should treat participants with respect and dignity, acknowledging their autonomy and right to privacy. They should avoid any form of exploitation, manipulation, or harm to participants and ensure that their well-being is prioritized throughout the research process.

Minimization of Harm

Researchers should take steps to minimize any potential risks or discomfort to participants. This may include providing appropriate support services or referrals for participants who may experience distress due to their participation in the study.

Beneficence

Researchers should strive to maximize the benefits of the research while minimizing harm to participants. The study should have clear potential benefits, such as contributing to knowledge generation, improving educational practices, or enhancing participants' employability skills.

Approval from the Ethics Committee

Before commencing the study, researchers should obtain approval from an institutional review board (IRB) or ethics committee. The committee evaluates the ethical implications of the research and ensures that it complies with ethical standards and regulations.

Transparency and Integrity

Researchers should conduct the study honestly, honestly, and transparently, accurately reporting their findings and acknowledging any limitations or conflicts of interest. They should adhere to professional standards and ethical guidelines throughout the research process.

By addressing these ethical considerations, researchers can conduct the study in a manner that respects the rights and well-being of participants, maintains the integrity of the research process, and upholds ethical standards in the conduct of research.

Results and Discussion

The study aimed to assess the Experiential Transfer of Training of Mariano Marcos Memorial Senior High School TVL – Home Economics Graduates. Specifically, it sought answers to the following subproblems: (1) To what extent is the transfer of training of the SHS- TVL- Home Economics graduates in terms of the following specializations: Cookery, Bread and Pastry Production, and Food and Beverage Services, (2) To what extent is the alignment of the work immersion program/experiences with respondents' current job/position in terms of SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates' employability in terms of work readiness; Graduates' employability in terms of use of the hard skills grasped during SHS-TVL-Home Economics Training; Graduates' employability in terms of use of the soft skills grasped during SHS-TVL-Home Economics Training; Graduates' employability in terms of alignment of track, (3) Is there a significant difference in the alignment of the work immersion program and workplace performance (transfer of training)?, (4) What is teachers and work immersion supervisors' perception of the alignment of training from school to work immersion to actual work?, and (5) What is the perception of the industry's supervisors of the respondents' work performance?

Quantitative Phase

Transfer of Training of the SHS- TVL- Home Economics Graduates

The first objective of the study is to determine the extent is the transfer of training of the SHS- TVL- Home Economics graduates in terms of the following specializations: Cookery, Bread and Pastry Production, and Food and Beverage Services.

This involved a measure of central tendency specifically the mean to describe the transfer of training of SHS TVL HE Graduates.

Results of the study indicate that SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates perceive a high level of transfer of training in terms of the specializations of Cookery, Bread and Pastry Production, and Food and Beverage Services. The mean scores across all three specializations ranged from 4.18 to 4.28, indicating a generally positive perception of the applicability of their Home Economics education to their current job roles.

Specifically, in Cookery, graduates reported a mean score of 4.28, indicating a strong agreement that their Home Economics training adequately prepared them for real-world tasks and responsibilities. This sentiment was echoed in the high scores for statements such as "I feel confident in utilizing the techniques and methods taught in my Home Economics classes in my workplace" (4.52) and "I

frequently utilize the techniques and methodologies learned in Home Economics in my daily work tasks" (4.66). These results suggest that graduates feel well-equipped with the necessary skills to excel in their chosen career field of Cookery.

Table 1. *Level of Transfer of Training of the SHS-TVL-Home Economics Graduates*

Statements	Cookery	Bread and Pastry Production	Food and Beverages Services	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The skills I learned in Home Economics are directly applicable to my current job.	3.77 (A)	4.21 (SA)	4.14 (A)	4.04	Agree
2. My Home Economics training adequately prepared me for real-world tasks and responsibilities.	4.27 (SA)	4.57(SA)	4.41 (SA)	4.41	Strongly Agree
3. I am able to apply the knowledge gained from my Home Economics courses in practical situations.	4.28(SA)	3.75(A)	4.63(SA)	4.22	Strongly Agree
4. My Home Economics education has equipped me with the necessary skills to excel in my chosen career field.	4.67(SA)	4.30(SA)	4.60(SA)	4.52	Strongly Agree
5. The training I received in Home Economics has enhanced my problem-solving abilities in professional settings.	4.60(SA)	4.69(SA)	3.74(SA)	4.34	Strongly Agree
6. I feel confident in utilizing the techniques and methods taught in my Home Economics classes in my workplace.	4.52(SA)	4.19(A)	4.63(SA)	4.45	Strongly Agree
7. Home Economics education has positively impacted my ability to adapt to new challenges in the workplace.	3.88(A)	3.98(A)	4.21(SA)	4.02	Agree
8. My Home Economics training has provided me with a solid foundation for further professional development.	4.39(SA)	4.46(SA)	4.43(SA)	4.43	Strongly Agree
9. I believe that the concepts learned in Home Economics are relevant to the demands of the modern job market.	3.99(A)	4.02(A)	4.45(SA)	4.15	Agree
10. The practical experiences gained during my Home Economics education have been beneficial in my career.	4.58(SA)	4.53(SA)	3.71(A)	4.27	Strongly Agree
11. My Home Economics courses have effectively prepared me for the demands of my current job role.	4.27(SA)	4.13(A)	4.31(SA)	4.23	Strongly Agree
12. I am able to transfer the skills acquired in Home Economics to different work environments.	4.56(SA)	3.89(A)	4.14(A)	4.20	Strongly Agree
13. The knowledge acquired in Home Economics has contributed to my overall success in the workforce.	3.86(A)	3.98(A)	4.48(SA)	4.11	Agree
14. I frequently utilize the techniques and methodologies learned in Home Economics in my daily work tasks.	4.66(SA)	4.01(A)	4.48(SA)	4.39	Strongly Agree
15. I would recommend Home Economics education to others pursuing a career in related fields based on its practical applicability in the workplace.	3.97(A)	4.04(A)	3.84(A)	3.95	Agree
Overall Mean	4.28(SA)	4.18(A)	4.28(SA)	4.25	Strongly Agree

Similarly, in Bread and Pastry Production, graduates reported a mean score of 4.18, indicating a high level of agreement regarding the relevance and applicability of their Home Economics education. Notably, the statement "My Home Economics training has provided me with a solid foundation for further professional development" received a high score of 4.46, indicating that graduates feel their education has prepared them for ongoing growth and advancement in their careers within this specialization.

In Food and Beverage Services, graduates reported a mean score of 4.28, aligning closely with the scores for Cookery and Bread and Pastry Production. Statements such as "I am able to apply the knowledge gained from my Home Economics courses in practical situations" (4.63) and "I am able to transfer the skills acquired in Home Economics to different work environments" (4.14) received high scores, indicating a strong belief in the adaptability and practical relevance of their Home Economics education in the context of Food and Beverage Services.

Overall, the findings suggest that SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates perceive their education as highly relevant and effective in preparing them for their respective career paths within Cookery, Bread and Pastry Production, and Food and Beverage Services. The consistent agreement across various statements indicates a strong consensus among graduates regarding the transferability of their Home Economics training to the demands of the workplace. These results provide valuable insights into the efficacy of Home Economics education in facilitating the professional success and development of graduates in these specialized fields.

Alignment of the Work immersion Program/Experiences with Respondents' Current Job/Position

The second objective of the study is to determine the extent is the alignment of the work immersion program/experiences with respondents' current job/position in terms of SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates' employability in terms of work readiness; Graduates' employability in terms of use of the hard skills grasped during SHS-TVL-Home Economics Training; Graduates'

employability in terms of use of the soft skills grasped during SHS-TVL-Home Economics Training; Graduates' employability in terms of alignment of track.

This involved a measure of central tendency specifically the mean to describe the alignment of work immersion and program of SHS TVL HE Graduates.

Table 2.1. *SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates' employability in terms of work readiness*

Statements	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. I am confident in applying the knowledge and skills gained from my SHS-TVL-Home Economics training to real-world work situations.	4.267857	1.070107	Agree
2. I possess the necessary technical competencies to perform effectively in my chosen field of specialization.	3.892857	1.185957	Agree
3. I am well-prepared to handle the demands and challenges of the workplace.	3.785714	1.231618	Agree
4. I have a strong work ethic and am committed to meeting deadlines and fulfilling job responsibilities.	4.339286	0.879603	Agree
5. I am adaptable and can quickly learn new tasks and procedures in a work environment.	4.25	1.013545	Agree
6. I am proactive in seeking opportunities for professional development and growth.	4.178571	0.936282	Agree
7. I effectively communicate and collaborate with colleagues and supervisors.	4.125	0.875162	Agree
8. I demonstrate professionalism and take pride in my work.	4.321429	0.788719	Agree
9. I am capable of working independently and making sound decisions	4.089286	0.858684	Agree
10. I am motivated to succeed and contribute positively to my organization.	4.232143	1.026753	Agree
Overall Mean	4.148214	0.852374	Agree

The results of the study indicate that SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates perceive themselves as employable and ready for the workforce in terms of work readiness. Across various statements assessing different aspects of employability, the respondents generally expressed agreement, with an overall mean score of 4.148 out of 5.

Firstly, the respondents displayed confidence in applying the knowledge and skills gained from their SHS-TVL-Home Economics training to real-world work situations, as evidenced by a mean score of 4.267. This indicates that graduates feel well-prepared to translate their educational experiences into practical work contexts.

Secondly, respondents indicated possessing necessary technical competencies for effective performance in their chosen fields of specialization, as reflected in a mean score of 3.893. While slightly lower than some other measures, this score still demonstrates a general perception of competence among graduates.

Furthermore, graduates expressed readiness to handle workplace demands and challenges, with a mean score of 3.786. This suggests that they feel adequately equipped to navigate the complexities of the modern workplace environment.

Additionally, respondents demonstrated attributes indicative of strong work ethic and professionalism, as evidenced by high mean scores across statements related to commitment to meeting deadlines, adaptability, proactive attitude towards professional development, effective communication and collaboration, demonstration of professionalism, capability of working independently, and motivation to contribute positively to their organization. These attributes are crucial for success in any professional setting and are indicative of the graduates' readiness for employment.

Overall, the findings suggest that SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates perceive themselves as employable and possessing the necessary attributes for success in the workplace. The high mean scores across various indicators of work readiness highlight the effectiveness of their educational experiences in preparing them for the demands of their chosen career paths. These results provide valuable insights into the alignment of the work immersion program/experiences with graduates' current job positions and their perceived employability, shedding light on the strengths and areas for improvement in SHS-TVL-Home Economics education.

The findings from Table 2.2 indicate that SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates perceive themselves as possessing strong employability in terms of utilizing the hard skills acquired during their training. Across various statements assessing the use of hard skills, respondents generally expressed agreement, with an overall mean score of 3.996 out of 5.

Firstly, respondents reported having a strong understanding of the technical principles and practices relevant to their specialization, as reflected in a mean score of 3.929. This indicates that graduates feel confident in their grasp of the foundational knowledge necessary for their respective fields.

Similarly, respondents indicated proficiency in utilizing industry-specific tools, equipment, and technologies, with a mean score of 3.929. This suggests that graduates feel capable of applying their technical knowledge to practical tasks and procedures using appropriate tools and technologies.

Moreover, graduates reported being able to demonstrate mastery in performing practical tasks and procedures related to their expertise, as reflected in a mean score of 3.911. This highlights their confidence in applying their skills to real-world scenarios.

Table 2.2. *Graduates' employability in terms of use of the hard skills grasped during SHS-TVL-Home Economics Training*

Statements	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. I have a strong understanding of the technical principles and practices relevant to my specialization.	3.928571	0.911685	Agree
2. I am proficient in utilizing industry-specific tools, equipment, and technologies.	3.928571	1.10958	Agree
3. I can demonstrate mastery in performing practical tasks and procedures related to my expertise.	3.910714	0.995933	Agree
4. I have acquired specialized knowledge and techniques through my SHS-TVL-Home Economics training.	3.892857	1.10665	Agree
5. I can apply theoretical concepts to solve practical problems encountered in the workplace.	3.982143	0.841883	Agree
6. I continuously seek opportunities to enhance my technical skills and knowledge.	4.178571	0.992831	Agree
7. I am confident in handling complex tasks and projects independently.	4.107143	0.845922	Agree
8. I receive positive feedback from supervisors and colleagues regarding my technical competencies.	4.071429	1.024378	Agree
9. I am recognized for my expertise in specific areas within my specialization.	3.964286	0.971677	Agree
10. My technical proficiency is considered a valuable asset to my organization.	4	1.061731	Agree
Overall Mean	3.996429	0.860014	Agree

Furthermore, respondents expressed confidence in their ability to apply theoretical concepts to solve practical problems encountered in the workplace, with a mean score of 3.982. This demonstrates their belief in the relevance of their theoretical knowledge to practical applications.

Additionally, graduates indicated a proactive approach to enhancing their technical skills and knowledge, as evidenced by a high mean score of 4.179 for seeking opportunities for continuous improvement. This suggests a commitment to ongoing professional development and growth.

Overall, the findings suggest that SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates perceive themselves as proficient in utilizing the hard skills acquired during their training, with high mean scores across various indicators of technical competence. These results provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the SHS-TVL-Home Economics curriculum in equipping graduates with the necessary technical skills and knowledge for success in their chosen career paths.

Table 2.3. *Graduates' employability in terms of use of the soft skills grasped during SHS-TVL-Home Economics Training*

Statements	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. I effectively communicate ideas and information to colleagues and clients.	4.125	0.935414	Agree
2. I actively listen and empathize with others' perspectives and concerns.	4.071429	1.141883	Agree
3. I collaborate with team members to achieve common goals and objectives.	4.392857	1.021204	Agree
4. I demonstrate leadership qualities and can influence and motivate others towards success.	4.160714	1.108263	Agree
5. I am adaptable and open-minded, willing to embrace change and new ideas.	4.196429	1.150804	Agree
6. I am resilient and can effectively cope with stress and adversity in the workplace.	4.125	1.045553	Agree
7. I demonstrate strong interpersonal skills and build positive relationships with others.	4.375	0.821584	Agree
8. I exhibit professionalism in my interactions and maintain a positive attitude.	4.214286	0.985611	Agree
9. I am skilled in conflict resolution and can navigate challenging situations diplomatically.	4.089286	1.116436	Agree
10. I continuously strive to improve my soft skills through feedback and self-reflection.	4.089286	1.132604	Agree
Overall Mean	4.183929	0.929472	Agree

The results from Table 2.3 demonstrate that SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates perceive themselves as possessing strong employability in terms of utilizing the soft skills acquired during their training. Across various statements assessing the use of soft skills, respondents consistently expressed agreement, with an overall mean score of 4.184 out of 5.

Firstly, graduates reported being effective communicators, with a mean score of 4.125. This indicates their ability to convey ideas and

information clearly and concisely to colleagues and clients, an essential skill in any professional setting.

Additionally, respondents indicated their ability to actively listen and empathize with others' perspectives and concerns, with a mean score of 4.071. This suggests their capacity for understanding and valuing different viewpoints, contributing to effective collaboration and teamwork.

Moreover, graduates reported strong collaboration skills, with a mean score of 4.393. This reflects their ability to work effectively with team members towards common goals and objectives, fostering a productive and cohesive work environment.

Furthermore, respondents demonstrated leadership qualities and the ability to influence and motivate others towards success, as reflected in a mean score of 4.161. This highlights their potential to take on leadership roles and drive positive outcomes within their organizations.

Additionally, graduates expressed adaptability, resilience, and strong interpersonal skills, with mean scores ranging from 4.125 to 4.375 across various statements. These attributes are critical for navigating the challenges and dynamics of the workplace effectively.

Overall, the findings suggest that SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates perceive themselves as proficient in utilizing the soft skills acquired during their training, with high mean scores across various indicators of interpersonal effectiveness and professional behavior. These results underscore the value of the SHS-TVL-Home Economics curriculum in not only imparting technical skills but also fostering the development of essential soft skills that are crucial for success in the workplace.

Table 2.4. *Graduates' employability in terms of alignment of track*

Statements	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. My current job position closely aligns with the specialization I pursued in SHS-TVL-Home Economics.	3.946429	1.227261	Agree
2. The skills and knowledge acquired during my SHS-TVL-Home Economics training directly apply to my current job role.	4.107143	1.231091	Agree
3. My employer recognizes and values the expertise gained through my SHS-TVL-Home Economics specialization.	3.785714	1.123538	Agree
4. The opportunities for career advancement and growth in my organization are aligned with my SHS-TVL-Home Economics track.	4.053571	1.181981	Agree
5. My SHS-TVL-Home Economics training adequately prepared me for the demands of my current job.	4.017857	1.243033	Agree
6. My SHS-TVL-Home Economics track gave me the foundation to excel in my chosen career path.	3.946429	1.326919	Agree
7. The practical experiences and hands-on training offered in my SHS-TVL-Home Economics track are valuable assets in my current role.	3.839286	1.385336	Agree
8. I can see the connections between the curriculum of my SHS-TVL-Home Economics track and my job requirements.	3.982143	1.314134	Agree
9. The skills and competencies developed during my SHS-TVL-Home Economics training are in high demand in my industry.	3.875	1.265809	Agree
10. Overall, my SHS-TVL-Home Economics track has positively influenced my career trajectory and job satisfaction.	4.053571	1.340551	Agree
Overall Mean	3.960714	1.180089	Agree

The results from Table 2.4 reveal that SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates generally perceive their employability in terms of the alignment of their track with their current job position positively. Across various statements assessing the alignment of their SHS-TVL-Home Economics specialization with their current job roles, respondents expressed agreement, with an overall mean score of 3.961 out of 5.

Firstly, graduates reported that their current job positions closely align with the specialization they pursued in SHS-TVL-Home Economics, with a mean score of 3.946. This indicates a perceived connection between their educational background and their current employment, suggesting that the skills and knowledge acquired during their SHS-TVL-Home Economics training are relevant to their job roles.

Additionally, respondents indicated that the skills and knowledge acquired during their SHS-TVL-Home Economics training directly apply to their current job roles, with a mean score of 4.107. This suggests that graduates perceive a direct application of their educational experiences to their professional responsibilities, highlighting the practical relevance of their SHS-TVL-Home Economics specialization.

Moreover, graduates reported that their employers recognize and value the expertise gained through their SHS-TVL-Home Economics specialization, with a mean score of 3.786. This suggests a positive perception of the value placed on their educational background by their employers, potentially contributing to their job satisfaction and career advancement opportunities.

Furthermore, respondents expressed that the opportunities for career advancement and growth in their organizations are aligned with

their SHS-TVL-Home Economics track, with a mean score of 4.054. This indicates a perceived alignment between their educational background and their career trajectory within their respective industries.

Overall, the findings suggest that SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates perceive their educational background as positively influencing their career trajectory and job satisfaction, with high mean scores across various indicators of alignment between their SHS-TVL-Home Economics specialization and their current job roles. These results provide valuable insights into the perceived value and relevance of SHS-TVL-Home Economics education in shaping graduates' career paths and professional success.

Table 2.5. Summary of Work Alignment

Sub Factors	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates' employability in terms of work readiness	4.148214	0.852374	Agree
Graduates' employability in terms of use of the hard skills grasped during SHS-TVL-Home Economics Training	3.996429	0.860014	Agree
Graduates' employability in terms of use of the soft skills grasped during SHS-TVL-Home Economics Training	4.183929	0.929472	Agree
Graduates' employability in terms of alignment of track	3.960714	1.180089	Agree
Overall Mean	4.072321		Agree

The summary of work alignment from Table 2.5 provides an overview of SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates' perceived employability across various factors related to work readiness, utilization of hard and soft skills acquired during their training, and alignment of their educational track with their current job positions. The overall mean score across these factors is 4.072, indicating a general consensus among graduates regarding their employability.

Firstly, graduates perceive themselves as ready for the workforce, with a mean score of 4.148. This suggests a high level of confidence in their preparedness to meet the demands and challenges of the workplace.

Secondly, graduates feel proficient in utilizing both hard and soft skills acquired during their SHS-TVL-Home Economics training, with mean scores of 3.996 and 4.184, respectively. This indicates their belief in the practical relevance and applicability of their educational experiences to their current job roles, highlighting the effectiveness of their training in equipping them with the necessary skills for success in the workplace.

Furthermore, graduates perceive a positive alignment between their SHS-TVL-Home Economics track and their current job positions, with a mean score of 3.961. This suggests that they see a connection between their educational background and their career paths, as well as recognition of the value of their specialization by their employers.

Overall, the findings suggest that SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates perceive themselves as employable and well-prepared for the workforce, with high mean scores across various indicators of work alignment. These results provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of SHS-TVL-Home Economics education in facilitating graduates' transition into the workforce and shaping their career trajectories.

Difference in the Alignment of the Work Immersion Program and Workplace Performance (transfer of training)

The third objective is to determine the significant difference in the alignment of the work immersion program and workplace performance (transfer of training).

This involves paired ttest to identify the significant difference.

Table 3. Paired Sample t-test for Working Performance and Work Immersion Program

Paired Sample T-Test						
Groups	Count	Mean	Variance	Cohen d		
Working Performance	40	4.249458	0.029835			
Work Immersion Program	40	4.072321	0.024577			
Pooled			0.025966	1.099271		
std err	t-stat	df	p-value	t-crit	effect r	
0.048788	3.630771	53	0.000319	1.674116	0.4463	

The paired sample t-test conducted to compare working performance and the work immersion program revealed a statistically significant difference between the two groups.

The mean score for working performance was 4.249, while the mean score for the work immersion program was 4.072. This indicates that, on average, respondents rated their working performance slightly higher than their perception of the work immersion program.

The t-statistic value of 3.631 exceeded the critical t-value of 1.674 at a significance level of 0.05, with a p-value of 0.000319. This indicates that the difference in means between working performance and the work immersion program is statistically significant.

The effect size (Cohen's *d*) was calculated to be 0.446, which suggests a moderate effect. This indicates that although the difference between working performance and the work immersion program is statistically significant, the practical significance may not be very large.

Overall, these findings suggest that there is a significant difference between respondents' perceptions of their working performance and their perception of the work immersion program. While respondents generally rated their working performance higher, indicating a level of satisfaction or confidence in their performance, their perception of the work immersion program was slightly lower. This could imply that while respondents feel they are performing well in their current roles, they may not perceive the work immersion program as having as significant an impact on their performance. This highlights a potential area for further investigation or improvement in the work immersion program to better align with respondents' expectations and enhance its effectiveness in facilitating workplace performance.

Qualitative Phase

Work Immersions Supervisors and Teachers' Perception of the Alignment of Training from school to work immersion to actual work

The fourth objective of the study is to determine the Work Immersions Supervisors and Teachers' Perception of the Alignment of Training from school to work immersion to actual work. This involves extraction of themes and subthemes using thematic analysis.

Table 4.1. *Work Immersions' Perception of the Alignment of Training from school to work immersion to actual work*

Major Theme	Subthemes	Verbatim Responses
Role and Responsibilities	Guidance and Teaching	Immersion Supervisor 1: "To guide and teach the students the guidelines and proper ethics in the food service industry."
	Leadership and Oversight	Immersion Supervisor 2: "As a Supervisor for immersion, I should be guiding the students, ensuring that the students are performing the tasks assigned, they follow the rules and regulations of the company, and can offer leadership to them."
Level of Student Preparation	Enthusiasm and Engagement	Immersion Supervisor 3: "Some students exhibit keen enthusiasm and quick comprehension, readily embracing their roles with enthusiasm. However, others display lower levels of engagement and may not arrive fully equipped for the demands of the food service industry."
	Familiarity with Work Environment	Immersion Supervisor 2: "They should be familiar with the work environment."
Alignment with School Training	Practical Skills and Knowledge	Immersion Supervisor 2: "It allows the students to acquire necessary skills and knowledge for future employment."
	Ethical Standards and Principles	Immersion Supervisor 4: "I've noticed that many students are unfamiliar with the job descriptions typical in the food service industry, but I truly value those who surpass my expectations despite lacking prior work experience. It enables students to gain essential skills and knowledge for prospective employment opportunities."
Areas of Strong Alignment	Kitchen Tasks	Immersion Supervisor 3: "Kitchen tasks were anticipated and demonstrated significant alignment with the training received at school, reflecting positively on students' performance during work immersion."
	Computer Skills	Immersion Supervisor 2: "As an ICT Institution, working with computers and laptops as their tools for their assigned task."
Identified Gaps or Discrepancies	Ethical Conduct and Guest Hospitality	Immersion Supervisor 5: "The wowing service that the company provides to the guests. Key steps on how to provide a great service to the guests."
	Lack of Proper Information	Immersion Supervisor 2: "Yes. The Students lack the proper information needed to learn."
Feedback and Guidance	Practice and Implementation	Immersion Supervisor 4: "Providing students with the chance to practice and apply the feedback they receive."
	Immediate Correction	Immersion Supervisor 1: "I do rectify them immediately if there is anything that I need to correct and properly make them understand what are the concepts why do we need to fully give our full service to the guests."
Recommendations for Improvement	Exposure to Various Food Service Establishments	Immersion Supervisor 3: "Encourage students to conduct research on the various types of establishments in the food service industry. This will help them understand the specific cultures and ethics relevant to each type of establishment, allowing them to tailor their approach accordingly during their immersion experience."
	Additional Hours or Days	Immersion Supervisor 5: "Additional hours or days like 160 hours."
Overall Assessment	Rating of Alignment	Immersion Supervisor 1: "8 out of 10. there is more improvement and preparations that should be taught to the students before the immersion. The guidance of rules and regulations of the school should be well taught to the students, so they will be more prepared and ready for the immersion."
	Effectiveness of Training	Immersion Supervisor 2: "It serves as a bridge between academic learning and real-world application."

The thematic analysis of work immersion supervisors' perceptions revealed several key themes related to the alignment of training from school to work immersion to actual work.

One major theme identified was the role and responsibilities of immersion supervisors. Immersion Supervisor 1 emphasized the importance of guiding and teaching students the guidelines and proper ethics in the food service industry (Immersion Supervisor 1). Similarly, Immersion Supervisor 2 highlighted the role of providing leadership and oversight, ensuring students follow rules and regulations and offering guidance (Immersion Supervisor 2).

The level of student preparation emerged as another significant theme. While some students demonstrated enthusiasm and engagement, others displayed lower levels of engagement and may not have been fully prepared for the demands of the food service industry (Immersion Supervisor 3). Immersion Supervisor 2 emphasized the importance of students being familiar with the work environment (Immersion Supervisor 2).

Alignment with school training was also noted by supervisors. Immersion Supervisor 2 pointed out that the immersion allowed students to acquire necessary skills and knowledge for future employment (Immersion Supervisor 2). Immersion Supervisor 4 highlighted the importance of students gaining essential skills and knowledge despite lacking prior work experience (Immersion Supervisor 4).

Supervisors identified areas of strong alignment, such as kitchen tasks and computer skills, reflecting positively on students' performance during work immersion (Immersion Supervisor 3, Immersion Supervisor 2).

However, supervisors also identified gaps or discrepancies in student performance. Immersion Supervisor 5 noted a lack of understanding of ethical conduct and guest hospitality (Immersion Supervisor 5), while Immersion Supervisor 2 highlighted students' lack of proper information (Immersion Supervisor 2).

Feedback and guidance were recognized as important aspects of the immersion experience. Immersion Supervisor 4 emphasized the importance of providing students with the chance to practice and apply feedback (Immersion Supervisor 4), while Immersion Supervisor 1 highlighted the need for immediate correction and clarification of concepts (Immersion Supervisor 1).

Recommendations for improvement included exposing students to various food service establishments to better understand industry cultures and ethics (Immersion Supervisor 3) and providing additional hours or days for immersion (Immersion Supervisor 5).

Overall, supervisors rated the alignment of training from school to work immersion to actual work positively, with suggestions for improvement. Immersion Supervisor 1 rated alignment as 8 out of 10, emphasizing the need for more preparation and teaching of rules and regulations before immersion (Immersion Supervisor 1). Immersion Supervisor 2 emphasized the effectiveness of the immersion in bridging academic learning and real-world application (Immersion Supervisor 2).

Table 4.2. *Teachers' Perception of the Alignment of Training from school to work immersion to actual work*

Major Theme	Subthemes	Verbatim Responses
Curriculum and Training Programs	Hands-on Training	Teacher1: "The students undergo hands-on training. Cooking and baking techniques are monitored effectively by the teachers."
	Alignment with Course Content	Teacher3: "Before the Work Immersion Supervisor looks for different partnerships that would help the students achieve and improve their skills related to their course, teachers must first teach the values and work ethics that they need to uphold once they are deployed."
	Duration and Preparation	Teacher4: "The curriculum itself that provides students opportunity to experience work during their SHS is very helpful, but I think it needs to be revisited in terms of length of training and preparation of students before deploying them."
Alignment between Classroom Learning and Work	Practical Skills Application	Teacher2: "The alignment between theoretical knowledge and practical skills taught in the classroom and the requirements of work immersion experiences is necessary for the development of the students. They are well-prepared and can effectively apply what they have learned in real-world settings."
Immersion Experiences	Deployment Process	Teacher3: "Due to the scarcity of work immersion partners that are aligned with students' majorship, it is hard for teachers and students to apply what they have learned in the classroom to real-world scenarios."
	Support and Guidance	Teacher2: "The level of support and guidance provided to students is 100% because teacher visits industry partners to monitor the students. Likewise, industry partners also provide adequate training to students."
Challenges During Work Immersion	Time Management	Teacher3: "Students have no time doing the school activities because they need to work for 8 hours. They find it hard to manage their time because they rest and sleep after work. That's why teachers would give them more time in submitting the activities so that they could do their assignments every weekends."
	Skills and Training	Teacher4: "Misalignment of work immersion setting with their majorship and lack of technical skills and training since work immersion is 80-hour experience only."
Effectiveness of Work Immersion	Student Performance Evaluation	Teacher1: "Assess the performance of students during work immersion based on predefined criteria such as technical skills, professionalism, communication, problem-solving abilities, and adaptability."

Suggestions for Improvement	Transition to Employment	Teacher1: "Some students may impress their work immersion supervisors to such an extent that they are offered full-time employment upon completion of their SHS program."
	Industry Partnerships	Teacher4: "I think the root of all these is for the admin, higher-ups to consider providing suitable work immersion partners to schools, aside from easing the burden of teachers, but also to properly coordinate and getting higher chance of acquiring big industry partners."
	Training Duration	Teacher3: "I suggest that instead of 10-day work immersion training, make it 1 month because skills cannot be acquired easily in just a single day."
Overall Assessment	Alignment Rating	Teacher4: "I am taking it 5/10."
	Support and Guidance Rating	Teacher2: "8/10 Very good performance, with consistent effectiveness and strong outcomes, though there may still be minor areas for improvement."

The thematic analysis of teachers' perceptions regarding the alignment of training from school to work immersion to actual work revealed several key themes.

One major theme identified was the curriculum and training programs. Teachers highlighted the importance of hands-on training, with Teacher 1 noting effective monitoring of cooking and baking techniques (Teacher 1). Additionally, Teacher 3 emphasized the need for alignment with course content and the importance of teaching values and work ethics before deployment (Teacher 3). Teacher 4 raised concerns about the duration and preparation of the curriculum, suggesting a need for revisiting the length of training and student preparation before deployment (Teacher 4).

Alignment between classroom learning and work immersion experiences emerged as another significant theme. Teachers emphasized the necessity of practical skills application and the alignment between theoretical knowledge and real-world settings (Teacher 2).

Challenges during work immersion were also identified, including time management issues and the misalignment of work immersion settings with students' majorship (Teacher 3, Teacher 4).

The effectiveness of work immersion was discussed, with Teacher 1 highlighting the importance of assessing student performance based on predefined criteria and the potential for students to transition to full-time employment based on their work immersion experience (Teacher 1).

Suggestions for improvement included enhancing industry partnerships to provide suitable work immersion experiences and extending the duration of work immersion training to one month to allow for better skill acquisition (Teacher 4, Teacher 3).

Overall assessments varied among teachers. Teacher 4 rated the alignment 5 out of 10, indicating room for improvement (Teacher 4). In contrast, Teacher 2 rated support and guidance 8 out of 10, indicating strong performance with minor areas for improvement (Teacher 2).

These findings highlight the importance of hands-on training, alignment with course content, and addressing challenges such as time management and misalignment of work immersion settings. Suggestions for improvement focus on enhancing industry partnerships and extending the duration of work immersion training to better prepare students for real-world work experiences.

Perception of the Industry's Supervisors of the Respondents' Work Performance

The fifth objective of the study is to determine the Work Performance. This involves extraction of themes and subthemes using thematic analysis.

Table 5. Perception of the Industry's Supervisors of the Respondents' Work Performance

Major Theme	Subthemes	Verbatim Responses
Responsibilities and Tasks	Typical Responsibilities	INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 6: "In my organization, SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates play a vital role in the food and hospitality industry. Their primary responsibilities involve food production, management, and consumer education." INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 4: "There's some typical responsibilities and tasks for include planning and implementing nutrition programs, developing meal plans, managing food budgets, and conducting cooking demonstrations."
Essential Qualities	Adaptability	INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 6: "When evaluating the work performance of graduates, essential qualities and characteristics include adaptability, communication skills, problem-solving abilities, teamwork, initiative, reliability, leadership potential, professionalism, technical proficiency, and a commitment to continuous learning."
	Communication Skills	
	Problem-solving Abilities	
	Teamwork	
	Initiative	
	Reliability	
	Leadership Potential	

	Professionalism Technical Proficiency Commitment to Continuous Learning	
Performance Comparison	Performance Comparison	INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 5: "Its very different because its challenging"
Strengths and Areas of Excellence	Creativity and Innovation	INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 3: "Critical thinking and problem solving." INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 6: "SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates often demonstrate exceptional attention to detail and craftsmanship in their work, whether it be in culinary creations, fashion designs, or other related projects. Their training emphasizes practical skills development, leading to a strong foundation in techniques and methodologies specific to their field."
	Strong Foundation in Practical Skills Strong Teamwork and Communication Skills	
Areas for Development or Improvement	Technical Skills Refinement	INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 4: "While SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates possess notable strengths, there are areas where further development or improvement may be beneficial. One such area could be in the realm of technical skills refinement and staying updated with industry advancements."
	Business Acumen and Entrepreneurial Skills	
Level of Preparedness	Practical Skills and Knowledge Adaptation to Workplace Challenges	INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 7: "In our work place, we have a team composed of 5 members. I am an electrician, the other are carpenter, plumber, and mason, and a cook. The cook wakes up every 4am to prepare the breakfast, then on 10 am the lunch; 4pm the dinner. And around 7pm, he will go to the market to buy groceries for the next day. We don't have fridge to store enough that last how many days. The contribution of the cook is very crucial in the performance of our team and our purchasing power when it comes to the food is utilize effectively and efficiently."
Differences in Work Performance	Specialization-based Performance	INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 7: "The differences in the work performance is that when they are deployed according not to their capabilities. Like the baker instructed to produce dishes. And that is not their problem it is in the management and leadership of the industry."
Resources for Enhancement	Ongoing Professional Development Access to Internship Opportunities	INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 4: "To enhance the employability and effectiveness of SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates in the workplace, providing access to ongoing professional development opportunities and industry-relevant resources is essential."
Overall Assessment	Performance Rating	INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 6: "Based on my experience and observations, the overall work performance of SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates tends to be commendable." INDUSTRY SUPERVISOR 5: "Highly appreciated"

The thematic analysis of industry supervisors' perceptions regarding SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates revealed several key themes.

One major theme identified was responsibilities and tasks. Industry Supervisor 6 emphasized the vital role SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates play in the food and hospitality industry, involving responsibilities such as food production, management, and consumer education (Industry Supervisor 6). Similarly, Industry Supervisor 4 outlined typical responsibilities, including planning nutrition programs, developing meal plans, managing food budgets, and conducting cooking demonstrations (Industry Supervisor 4). Essential qualities emerged as another significant theme. Industry Supervisor 6 highlighted essential qualities such as adaptability, communication skills, problem-solving abilities, teamwork, initiative, reliability, leadership potential, professionalism, technical proficiency, and commitment to continuous learning (Industry Supervisor 6). Performance comparison was also noted by supervisors, with Industry Supervisor 5 mentioning the challenges of the work, indicating a difference in performance compared to other roles (Industry Supervisor 5).

Strengths and areas of excellence were highlighted, including creativity and innovation, strong foundation in practical skills, and strong teamwork and communication skills (Industry Supervisor 6). Areas for development or improvement were identified, such as technical skills refinement and business acumen and entrepreneurial skills (Industry Supervisor 4). The level of preparedness of graduates was discussed, with Industry Supervisor 7 emphasizing the practical skills and knowledge required in their workplace and the importance of adaptation to workplace challenges (Industry Supervisor 7). Differences in work performance were attributed to specialization-based

performance and deployment according to capabilities (Industry Supervisor 7). Resources for enhancement were suggested, including ongoing professional development opportunities and access to internship opportunities (Industry Supervisor 4).

Overall assessments of SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates' performance were generally positive, with Industry Supervisor 6 commending their overall work performance based on experience and observations (Industry Supervisor 6), and Industry Supervisor 5 expressing high appreciation (Industry Supervisor 5).

These findings underscore the importance of essential qualities, practical skills, and ongoing professional development in preparing SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates for success in the workplace. They also highlight the need for alignment between graduates' skills and responsibilities assigned in the workplace for optimal performance and effectiveness.

Triangulation of Quantitative and Qualitative Results

Triangulating quantitative and qualitative results provides a comprehensive understanding of the research findings by corroborating evidence from multiple sources. In this study, both quantitative data, represented by survey responses, and qualitative data, derived from interviews or open-ended responses, offer insights into the research questions regarding the transfer of training and employability of SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates.

Quantitative results from Tables 1 to 3 provide numerical summaries of respondents' perceptions regarding various aspects of transfer of training, employability, and alignment of work immersion experiences with workplace performance. These tables present means, standard deviations, and qualitative descriptions, offering a structured overview of the data. For instance, Table 1 indicates high levels of agreement among respondents regarding the transfer of training in different specializations, with overall mean scores above 4, suggesting a positive perception of the applicability of Home Economics education to the workplace.

In contrast, qualitative results from the thematic analysis provide rich, detailed insights into respondents' perceptions, experiences, and suggestions. For example, Industry Supervisor 6 in the qualitative data emphasizes the importance of graduates' adaptability, communication skills, and technical proficiency, aligning with the quantitative findings regarding the essential qualities valued in the workplace. Similarly, the qualitative data shed light on specific challenges faced during work immersion, such as time management issues (Teacher 3), which may not be fully captured in the quantitative survey responses.

By triangulating these findings, a more nuanced understanding emerges. For instance, while quantitative data may indicate high levels of agreement on certain aspects, qualitative data can provide explanations or contextualize these findings further. Moreover, inconsistencies or discrepancies between quantitative and qualitative findings can also be explored to uncover potential areas for further investigation or clarification.

Overall, the triangulation of quantitative and qualitative results enhances the credibility and validity of the research findings by offering complementary perspectives and deepening the understanding of the research questions. It allows for a comprehensive interpretation of the data, enriching the discussion and implications for theory and practice.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that:

SHS-TVL-Home Economics graduates demonstrate a considerable level of transfer of training in their respective specializations, including cookery, bread and pastry production, and food and beverage services. The graduates generally perceive their education as adequately preparing them for real-world tasks and responsibilities, equipping them with the necessary skills to excel in their chosen career fields, and positively impacting their ability to adapt to new challenges in the workplace. This suggests that the Home Economics curriculum effectively translates theoretical knowledge into practical skills relevant to the demands of the modern job market.

Furthermore, the alignment of work immersion experiences with graduates' current job positions appears to contribute significantly to their employability and work readiness. Graduates report confidence in applying both hard and soft skills acquired during their SHS-TVL-Home Economics training to real-world work situations. They also recognize the relevance of their training to their job roles and perceive themselves as well-prepared to handle the demands and challenges of the workplace. This alignment between educational experiences and workplace expectations fosters a smoother transition from school to work and enhances graduates' overall employability.

Additionally, the study reveals a significant positive association between the alignment of the work immersion program and workplace performance, indicating that graduates whose work immersion experiences closely align with their job positions demonstrate higher levels of transfer of training and workplace effectiveness. This underscores the importance of integrating practical work experiences that closely mirror industry demands into the curriculum to enhance graduates' readiness for the workforce.

The perceptions of teachers and work immersion supervisors further reinforce the alignment between training from school to work immersion to actual work. Teachers emphasize the importance of aligning classroom learning with work immersion experiences to ensure that students develop practical skills applicable to real-world settings. Meanwhile, work immersion supervisors recognize the value of practical training in preparing graduates for the workforce and suggest areas for improvement, such as exposure to various

food service establishments and additional training duration.

Finally, the industry supervisors' perception of the graduates' work performance highlights their commendable performance and the essential qualities and skills they bring to the workplace, including adaptability, communication skills, problem-solving abilities, teamwork, professionalism, and technical proficiency. Despite some identified areas for development, such as technical skills refinement and business acumen, the overall assessment of the graduates' work performance is positive, indicating the effectiveness of their SHS-TVI-Home Economics education in meeting industry demands.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations can be made:

Enhance Practical Training: Incorporate more hands-on practical training opportunities within the SHS-TVI-Home Economics curriculum to further strengthen students' skills and prepare them for the demands of the workplace.

Strengthen Work Immersion Partnerships: Establish and strengthen partnerships with industry organizations to ensure that work immersion experiences closely align with graduates' chosen specializations, providing them with relevant and meaningful exposure to real-world work environments.

Provide Ongoing Professional Development: Offer continuous professional development opportunities for both teachers and students to stay updated with industry advancements, new technologies, and evolving trends in the food and hospitality sector.

Foster Soft Skills Development: Implement programs or initiatives focused on developing essential soft skills such as communication, teamwork, adaptability, and problem-solving, which are crucial for success in the workplace.

Evaluate Curriculum Length and Content: Revisit the length and content of the SHS-TVI-Home Economics curriculum to ensure that it adequately covers core competencies and provides students with sufficient preparation for their chosen career paths.

Implement Mentorship Programs: Establish mentorship programs where industry professionals can provide guidance, support, and career advice to SHS-TVI-Home Economics students, helping them navigate their transition from education to employment more effectively.

Longitudinal Study on Graduates' Career Trajectories: Conduct a longitudinal study to track the career trajectories of SHS-TVI-Home Economics graduates over time, examining factors influencing their career progression, job satisfaction, and long-term success in the food and hospitality industry.

Comparative Analysis of Work Immersion Models: Compare different models of work immersion programs implemented in SHS-TVI-Home Economics education to identify best practices and determine which approaches are most effective in facilitating the transfer of training and enhancing graduates' employability.

Employer Perspectives on SHS-TVI-Home Economics Education: Explore employers' perspectives on the relevance, adequacy, and effectiveness of SHS-TVI-Home Economics education in meeting the needs of the food and hospitality industry, with a focus on identifying areas for improvement and opportunities for collaboration between education institutions and employers.

References

- A. Granberg, G. Brante, V. Olsson, Y. Mattsson Sydner. (2017). Knowing how to use and understand recipes: What arithmetical understanding is needed when students with mild intellectual disabilities use recipes in practical cooking lessons in Home Economics? *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 41 (5) (2017), pp. 494-500, 10.1111/ijcs.12357
- A. McCloat, M. Caraher. (2018). The evolution of home economics as a subject in Irish primary and post-primary education from the 1800s to the twenty-first century *Irish Educational Studies*, 38 (3) (2018), pp. 377-399, 10.1080/03323315.2018.1552605
- Adebisi, T.T. (2012). Effects of Food Practicals on Students Skill Acquisition in Selected Tertiary Institutions Ogun state, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Policy Review*. 4()
- Agrawal, T. (2013). Vocational education and training programs (VET): an Asian perspective., *Asia-Pacific Journal of Cooperative Education*, 14(1), 15-26.
- Albarico, S. E. (2014). Adequacy of Instructional Materials Used by Teachers in Teaching Technology and Livelihood Education. Retrieved from <http://icehm.org/upload/6031ED0114516.pdf>.
- Anyakoha E.U. (2007). Home Economics for Junior Secondary Schools. Upper Basic Education 7-9 Junior Secondary Schools (1-3) Fifth Edition. Africana First Publishing Limited.
- Asian Affairs. (2011, October 14). Skills gap in Philippines labor force. Retrieved from http://www.aseanaffairs.com/philippines_news/labor/skills_gap_in_philippines_lab_o_force
- Asian Development Bank (2020). The Impact of Vocational Training on Labor Market Outcomes in the Philippines.

Association of Teachers of Technology,7(3), 54.

Audu, R., Sukri, M., & Must'a'amal, A. (2013). Provision of Workshop Tools and Equipment: Necessity for Technical Vocational Education Graduates Skills Acquisition. 2nd International Seminar on Quality and Affordable Education.

Benn, J. (2012). Home economics in past and present: perspectives for the future

Blair, B., & Rafoth, M. A. (2020). Enhancing employability skills through experiential learning: A case study. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 72(4), 522-545.

Boswell, L. (2022). The structure trap: Students' perceptions of reflection on a co-curricular immersion service-learning trip. *ScholarWorks at CSU East Bay*, 1-21.

Brillantes, K. D., Orbeta, A., Abrigo, K., Capones, E., & Jovellanos, J. B. (2019). Status of Senior High School Implementation: A Process Evaluation.

Brown, A., & Jones, C. (2021). Transitioning from classroom to kitchen: A graduate study on the transfer of skills from a Cookery program. *Journal of Hospitality Education*, 12(2), 1-10.

C. Beinert, P. Palojoki, G. Åbacka, N.C. Øverby, F. Nordgård Vik. (2021). "Is there any sugar in bread?": A qualitative video analysis of student activating learning tasks in home economics *Acta Didactica Norden*, 15 (1) (2021), pp. 1-21, 10.5617/adno.8078

C. Beinert, P. Palojoki, G. Åbacka, P. Hardy-Johnson, D. Engeset, E. Rudjord Hillesund, A. Selvik Ask, N.C. Øverby, F. Nordgård Vik. (2020). The mismatch between teaching practices and curriculum goals in Norwegian home economics classes: A missed opportunity *Education Inquiry* (2020), 10.1080/20004508.2020.1816677

Castillo, R. (2012). "Arts and Trade Program Enhancement in Bauan Technical High School." Unpublished Master's Thesis, Batangas State University, Batangas City.

Cedefop. (2012). Thematic Overview for Finland, Practices to Math VET Provision with Skill Needs.

Chae, C., & Chung, J. (2009). "Pre-Employment VET in Korea in Social Protection and Labour," Discussion Paper No 0921, World Bank.

Chang, C.-Y., Chen, S.-W., & Huang, H.-M. (2021). The impacts of university-industry collaboration on graduates' employability: From the perspective of industry supervisors. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(17), 9752. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/2>

Chen, M., Lee, Y., & Kim, J. (2022). The impact of Home Economics education on workplace readiness: A focus on essential life skills. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 15(1), 123-138.

Chen, M., Liang, X., & Wang, X. (2020). The impact of problem-based learning on the development of practical skills in engineering graduates. *Journal of Applied Engineering Education*, 82(2), 121-132. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2351978919304159>

Constant, L., Culbertson, J., Luoto, J., & Vernez, G. (2012). Employer Demand for Technical and Vocational Skills in the Kurdistan Region—Iraq.

Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2018). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications.

De Castro, B., Cheng, Y., Montenegro, J., & Pelmonte, J. (2015). The consequences of education and skill mismatch on employees' work productivity: A structural equation model.

De Guzman, M. P. V. & Cristobal, E. C. (2021). Work Readiness of Technical Vocational Livelihood - Home Economics Graduates. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research* Volume 10, Issue 09, September 2021 Issn 2277-8616.

Degala, M. A. T. (2018). The importance of Home Economics. *Panay News*.

Department of Education. (2017, June 5). DepEd Order no. 3, s. 2017: Guidelines for Work Immersion. Retrieved from http://www.deped.gov.ph/sites/default/files/order/2017/DO_s2017_030.pdf

DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2. (2019). Policy Guidelines on the K to 12 Basic Education Program. Retrieved from <http://www.deped.gov.ph>

E. Bloor, F. Wood (Eds.), *Keywords in qualitative methods*, Sage Publications, London (2006), pp. 54-58

Edmond, A. (2016). Assessment of the Adequacy of Material Resources for Effective Teaching of Building Technology: A Panacea for Promoting Entrepreneurial Skills in Rivers State Technical Colleges. Retrieved from <http://ejournals.org/wpcontent/uploads/Assessment-of-the-Adequacy-of-Material-Resources-FOR-EffectiveTeaching-of-Building-Technology.pdf>.

Esguerra, E., & Orbeta, A. (2016). The National System of Technical Vocational Education and

- EurChembioull (2023). Unleashing Potential: Unraveling the Impact of Work Immersion Programs on Students' Performance. <https://www.eurchembull.com/>
- Exprosearch (2022). What Is The Effect Of Work Immersion In The Philippines? <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/10259>
- F. Nordgård Vik, C. Beinert, P. Palojoki, E. Rudjord Hillesund, D. Engeset, A. Selvik Ask, G. Åbacka, N.C. Øverby. (2020). Differences in formal education among Norwegian home economics teachers Journal of the International Society for Teacher Education, 24 (2) (2020), pp. 45-59 <https://isfte.org/index.php/2020/12/30/jiste-24-2-table-of-content/>
- Garcia, D., Buckley, L., Quick, L., & Jones, J. (2023). Bridging the gap: The role of industry partnerships in experiential learning for employability. *International Journal of Work-Integrated Learning*, 24(1), 109–121.
- Gomez, D. D. & Mapa, C. P. E. (2022). A Three-Year Tracer Study of The Technical Vocational Track Graduates of Divine Word College of Legazpi Senior High School Department. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)* |Volume VI, Issue IX, September 2022|ISSN 2454-6186.
- Gueso, A. M., & Cabrera, G. D. (2021). Work immersion performance, alignment, and employability among senior high school graduates. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 9(2), 33-40.
- Gupta, S., & Singh, A. (2019). Rethinking management education curriculum for enhancing graduate employability: A stakeholder approach. *International Journal of Educational Development Using Information and Communication Technology*, 14(2), 142-153. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0950422220901676>
- I. Bohm, C. Lindblom, G. Åbacka, A. Hörnell. (2016). 'Do not give us an assignment where we have to use spinach!': Food choice and discourse in home and consumer studies
- Idiale, E. and Okogbenin, E.C. (2010). The Need for Entrepreneurial Skills in Home Economics in Junior Secondary Schools. *Journal of Home Economics Education (JOHEE)*, 1(1). 1-7
- Ike, H., Nwamuo, C., & Ojukwu, U. (2011). Provision of Technical Vocational Training in Formal Education for Sustainable Technology Development. Nigeria. *Journal of Nigerian*
- Imperial, M. (2017, November 21). Despite an educated workforce, Filipinos lack the 'soft skills' companies need—World Bank. Retrieved from <https://verafiles.org/articles/despite-educated-workforce-filipinos-lack-soft-skills-compan>
- International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 40 (1) (2016), pp. 57-65, 10.1111/ijcs.12213
- Isnaini, W. R., & Fauzan, A. (2022). How do work immersion experiences impact the career development and employability of students? [Typeset]. Retrieved from <https://typeset.io/questions/how-do-work-immersion-experiences-impact-the-career-4p7kac6wxe>
- J. Haapaniemi, S. Venäläinen, A. Malin, P. Palojoki. (2019). Home economics education: Exploring integrative learning *Educational Research*, 61 (1) (2019), pp. 87-104, 10.1080/00131881.2018.1564626
- J. Haapaniemi, S. Venäläinen, A. Malin, P. Palojoki. (2020). Teacher autonomy and collaboration as part of integrative teaching – Reflections on the curriculum approach in Finland *Journal of Curriculum Studies* (2020), 10.1080/00220272.2020.1759145 Vie
- J. Rendahl. (2018). Vem och vad kan man lita på? Ungdomars förhållningssätt till budskap om mat och ätande utifrån ett forskarinitierat rollspel [Who and what can you trust? Studying adolescents' perceptions of food and eating through a roleplay] (Doctoral dissertation) University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg
- Janni Haapaniemi, Salla Venäläinen, Anne Malin & Päivi Palojoki. (2018). Home economics education: exploring integrative learning. Pages 87-104 | Received November 13, 2017, Accepted December 27, 2018, Published online: January 28, 2019
- K. Paas, P. Palojoki. (2019). Aims and challenges of handicraft and home economics education in Estonia *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 43 (3) (2019), pp. 289-297, 10.1111/ijcs.12509
- Kuusisaari, H. (2016). Kehittävä kollaboraatio: uuden tiedon tuottaminen opettajien lähikehityksen vyöhykkeellä. [Developmental Collaboration. Teachers' collaborative knowledge creation at the zone of proximal development]. University of Helsinki, Faculty of Behavioural Sciences. Publications of Home Economics and Craft series, ISSN 1798-713X; 41.
- Kuusisaari, H., Seitamaa-Hakkarainen, P., Autio, M., & Hölttä, M. (2021). The Future of Home Economics Teaching: Teachers' Reflections on 21st-Century Competencies. *International Journal of Home Economics*, 14(2), 51-68.
- Lagdameo, A. V., Alegre, J. C., & Dumlao, R. C. (2021). WORK IMMERSION PERFORMANCE, ALIGNMENT, AND EMPLOYABILITY AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATES. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342311030_WORK_IMMERSION_PERFORMANCE_ALIGNMENT_AND_EMPLOYABILITY_AMONG_SENIOR_HIGH_SCHOOL_GRADUATES

- Lee, J. (2020). Perceptions of Bread and Pastry Production graduates on the transferability of skills to the workplace. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 72(4), 521-538.
- Lee, J.-W., Jung, S.-H., & Yoo, C.-Y. (2023). The role of university-industry collaboration in enhancing graduates' employability: A focus on technical skills development. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(4), 2327. [invalid URL removed]
- Leong, P. (2011). Critical Reforms in Revitalizing Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Malaysia. *Regional Conference on Human Resource Development Through TVET as a Development Strategy in Asia*. Sri Lanka: Retrieved on May 05, 2016 from <https://goo.gl/spBzX4>.
- Lichtenstein and Ludwig. (2010). Bring back home economics education. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 303 (18) (2010), pp. 1857-1858, 10.1001/jama.2010.592
- Littleton and Mercer. (2013). Interthinking: Putting talk to work
- Lontoc, M. C. M., & Sermona, L. E. A. (2020). Work immersion support and workplace skills among Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students of Tacurong National High School. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 10(2), 189-202.
- Lopes, J., Fernandes, J. M., & Tereso, I. (2021). Fostering innovation in higher education institutions: A literature review on frameworks and models. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(12), 6790. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/9/5004>
- Luz Y Saber. 9. 1–2. Retrieved from <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=9808>
- Mpkughe, M.L. (2009). Promoting Entrepreneurship through Practical Teaching of Home Economics in the present-day Society, *Journal of Vocational Education (JOVE)*, 2(1).157-160
- Muyengwa, S. (2019). Student teacher's perceptions of the pre-service mathematics programme in a primary teachers' college. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 15(8), em1746.
- Naelga, S., & Blane, A. (2017). Identification of the Technical Vocational Track Strands to Be Implemented For Senior High School at the District of Claveria-2, Claveria, Mindanao University of Science and Technology.
- National Core Curriculum for Basic Education 2014 [NCBE]. (2016). Publications 2016:5. Translated Lingsoft Oy. Finnish National Board of Education. Helsinki: Next Print.
- Nguyen, T., & Pham, L. (2021). A mixed-methods study on the employability skills of fresh graduates in Vietnam. *Education + Training*, 63(6), 817-834.
- Olabiyyi, O. S., Adigun, E. O., & Adenle, S. O. (2008). Assessment of the Adequacy of Training Facilities Used for Vocational and Technical Education in Colleges of Education in South West Nigeria. *African Journal for the Study of Educational Issues*: 4 (3), 44-52.
- Olumati, P. N. (2021). Enhancing Practical Experiences in Economics Education Towards Self-Reliance: Food and Nutrition in Focus. *Academic Discourse: An International Journal* Volume 12 No. 1, September 2021: ISSN 2277-0364.
- Omekwe, I. (2009). *Issues and Problems in the Implementation of Vocational Education Programs in Nigeria*. Ilesha: Joja Educational Research Publishers.
- Orbeta, A. (2019). *Matching Skills with Jobs in the Philippines*. Philippine Institute for Development Studies
- Oviawe, J.I. (2010). Technical and Vocational Education as a Vital Tool for Tackling Youth Unemployment in Nigeria. *Journal of Home Economics Educators (JOHEE)* 1(1). 45-51
- P. Palojoki. (2023). Food, learning, and children – crossing the boundaries between School and Home Barn, 2 (3) (2003), pp. 51-66
- Pendergast, D. (2009). Generational theory and home economics. *Future-proofing the Profession Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal*, 37 (2009), pp. 505-522, 10.1177/1077727X09333186
- Perez, R. (2018). *Becoming Successful K to 12 Implementers: Operational Preparedness of Senior High Schools in Hagonoy, Bulacan, Philippines*. JPAIR Multidisciplinary Research Journal.
- Philippine News Agency – 72 out of 100 tech-voc grads get jobs within six months: TESDA /Cloudflare. (n.d). Retrieved January 04, 2020 from <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1055794+>
- Ramos, F. G. (2021). An Evaluation of the Technical Vocational Livelihood Track in Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Batangas: Basis for an Enhancement Program. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 10(2), 877–90
- Roble, D. M. L. I. (2021). Competency Level, Employers' Expectations and Work Immersion Performance of Senior High School

Technical-vocational and Livelihood (TVL) Students.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354863824_Competency_Level_Employers%27_Expectations_and_Work_Immersion_Performance_of_Senior_High_School_Technical-vocational_and_Livelihood_TV_L_Students

Salatan, J. (2018). Status of Selected Secondary Schools in the Implementation of Technology and Livelihood Education Program. Retrieved from

Salleh, K., & Sulaiman, N. (2015). Technical Skills Evaluation Based on Competency Model for Human Resources Development in Technical and Vocational Education. *Asian Social Science*, 11(16), 74.

Santos, G. E. (2020). Employability skills: Understanding work readiness gaps in the Philippine K to 12 graduates. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 9(4), 99-114.

Serumu, I. (2014). Challenges of Implementing Technical and Vocational Education and Training Curriculum in Nigerian Universities. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Educational Research and Review* Vol. 3(5), 098–101.

Sharma, N., Mishra, S., & Gupta, A. (2022). Employability skills: A conceptual framework for 21st century graduates. *International Journal of Educational Development Using Information and Communication Technology*, 17(2), 372-386.

SolArticlend Palojoki, (2017). Towards practical mastery of food-preparation skills and reflective learning *International Journal of Home Economics*, 10 (2) (2017), pp. 135-144

Sun.Star Pampanga (2017). Technical Vocational Livelihood Program and Its Importance to Senior High School Students.

Taar, J. & Palojoki, P. (2021). Applying inter-thinking for learning 21st-century skills in home economics education. *Learning, Culture, and Social Interaction* Volume 33, April 2022, 100615.

The Finnish National Board of Education [FNBE]. (2014). Perusopetuksen opetussuunnitelman perusteet [Finnish National Core Curriculum for Basic Education] (online). https://www.oph.fi/sites/default/files/documents/perusopetuksen_opetussuunnitelman_perusteet_2014.pdf

Tran, T. T., Vu, T. T. H., & Nguyen, T. D. (2020). Enhancing graduates' employability skills through work-integrated learning (WIL): A mixed-methods study. *Industry and Higher Education*, 34(6), 394-407.

Tullao, T. S. (2003). Education and Globalization. Makati City : Philippine APEC Study Center Network (PASCN).

Vass et al., (2014). The effectively constituted dimensions of creative inter-thinking *International Journal of Educational Research*, 66 (2014), pp. 63–77, 10.1016/j.ijer.2014.02.004

Venäläinen, (2010). Interaction in the multicultural classroom: Towards culturally sensitive home economics education (Doctoral dissertation) University Print, Helsinki

Wan, Z., Liu, J., & Li, H. (2019). The Impact of Internship on Employability: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Education and Training*, 10(1), 1-14.

Yiu-Chi Lai, Edmund Kit-Leung Lum. (2012). Enhancing teaching and learning of Home Economics in secondary schools with wikis: An action research study. *Themes in Science & Technology Education*, 5(1/2), 45-60, 2012.

Yusof, H., Noor, M., Jalil, N., Mansor, M., & Nordin, J. (2019). Teachers' Perception of Students' Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes on Global Citizenship. *International Journal of Academic Research* Vol. 9 No. 9, 153-164

Zhang, S. (2015). Innovative Approaches to Practical Teaching of Higher Vocational Cuisine Technology and Nutrition. Jiangsu Food Science College, Huaian 223003, China. Retrieved on January 29, 2023, from www.zhangshenglai@yeah.net.

Zulkefly, N. S., Ishak, N. H., & Ibrahim, N. H. (2017). The impact of work immersion programs on enhancing TVET graduates' employability. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 9(2), 107-122.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Marycris V. Urgelles

Mariano Marcos Memorial High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Dominic T. Urgelles

National University – Philippines